

VALUE AND EVALUATION IN ENGLISH AND GERMAN AXIOLOGICAL PHRASEOLOGY

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Abstract

The article reveals the concepts of value and evaluation in English and German axiological phraseology, which represent the “poles” of the value relationship of the subject to the object. Conventional values and anti-values are recorded indirectly in the content of linguistic units, which is expressed in the category of linguistic assessment. Being a verbalized result of the activity of consciousness, an assessment contains a positive or negative axiological characteristic of an object.

The relevance of the study is due to the versatility of such a phenomenon as value, which demonstrates the need for its comprehensive study. Values, national-cultural traditions and peculiarities of perception of the world are most succinctly, vividly and originally manifested in phraseological units, therefore the phraseological fund of a language seems to be one of the most interesting and productive objects of comparative research in the axiological aspect. Currently, axiological phraseology is a new and little-researched area of linguistics. It should be noted that in the phraseological fund, which a native speaker masters from childhood, norms of behavior in society are fixed, based on conventional values and anti-values.

The purpose of the research is to differentiate and reveal the concepts of value and evaluation based on the analysis of English and German axiological phraseological units.

The article emphasizes that an important criterion for identifying fundamental values is their binary nature, the presence of antonymic names that reflect the antinomic essence of values. Value can have both a positive and negative assessment, demonstrating the property of ambivalence. The implementation of evaluation occurs when an object is correlated with a value, reflecting the attitude of native speakers towards the object in terms of compliance or non-compliance of its qualities with certain value criteria.

As a result of the study, it was revealed that the estimated meaning of English and German axiological phraseological units (positive or negative) is determined using cultural information related to the etymology of phraseological units. In phraseology, evaluation can be expressed implicitly. To determine the axiological meaning of a phraseological unit in this case, its definition is required, as well as linguocultural information.

Keywords: Linguistics, language, value, evaluation, English, German, axiological phraseological unit, ambivalence.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of the categories of value and evaluation in the axiological phraseology of the English and German languages is of great practical importance, since the study of these concepts in foreign language classes at university contributes to the formation of a value system of students (Andreeva, Korneva, Kapustina, 2018; Andreeva, Korneva, Chugunov, 2022).

In axiology, values are considered meaning-forming elements of human existence that determine the direction and motivation of human life. Values unite people in community.

As researchers note, universal human values are based on goodness and reason, peacefulness and philanthropy, truth and beauty; they define moral and legal norms that reflect the historical spiritual experience of all humanity and create conditions for the realization of universal human interests (Yatsenko, 1999).

Values are socially approved and accepted by the majority of members of society. They are not questioned because they express the ideals and standards of behavior of people in a particular society. Values provide a person with life guidelines and determine the goals of his activities.

Anti-values are considered the opposite of values. Universal anti-values include a set of views and actions based on recklessness and evil, lies and selfishness, parasitism and aggressiveness (Yatsenko, 1999).

As important components of light culture, values are manifested in language. Linguistic evaluative means reveal the mechanism for reflecting conventional values and anti-values on which norms of behavior in society are based. In phraseological units, values, national-cultural traditions and peculiarities of worldview are realized most vividly and originally. For this reason, the phraseological fund of a language is one of the most interesting and productive objects of comparative research in the axiological aspect. It should be noted that axiological phraseology is a promising area of linguistic research.

2. DISCUSSION

An important criterion for identifying fundamental values is their binary nature, the presence of antonymic names that reflect the antinomic essence of values. The classification of conventional values and anti-values, represented by the phraseology of language, is presented in the works of L.K. Bayramova (Bayramova, 2008). Phraseological units are systematized according to axiological phraseological dyads (Bayramova, 2006, p. 82), which represent the unity of two blocks containing phraseological units whose semantics correlates with conventional values, and phraseological units whose semantics correlates with conventional anti-values. OK. Bayramova identifies the following values and anti-values: vital (life and death; health and illness); sacred (homeland and foreign land); hedonic (happiness and unhappiness); social-utilitarian (work and unemployment / laziness / rest); material and utilitarian (wealth and poverty); intellectual-cognitive (intelligence and stupidity); moral and ethical (truth and lies); emotional-utilitarian (laughter and crying); religious (heaven and hell) (Bayramova, 2008, p. 301).

The conventional values and anti-values are recorded indirectly in the content of linguistic units, which is expressed in the category of linguistic assessment. Interest in the problem of assessment is determined by the complexity of the phenomenon of assessment itself, which lies in the versatility of its structure, functioning in language and speech, and connection with the linguistic personality.

Philosophy examines the value relationship in its integrity. At the same time, value and evaluation represent the "poles" of a value relationship, which is defined as a consciously evaluating attitude of the subject to the object. This is a person's evaluative attitude towards objects and phenomena of the surrounding world. From the sphere of culture, norms, ideals, and patterns of behavior that reveal value meaning enter into human consciousness. Being a verbalized result of the activity of consciousness, the assessment contains a positive or negative axiological characteristic of an object, which is revealed when determining the degree of compliance of the object with the desires and needs of a person or socially established norms.

According to A.M. Yakhina, "it is necessary to distinguish between assessment and value: a value can be a phenomenon of the external world or a fact of thought, while assessment is a mental act that is the result of

a person's evaluative attitude towards this subject. The assessment is determined by standards established in society in the field of social, intellectual and moral phenomena, socially established norms and ideas about good and bad. The assessment is determined by the worldview of the people - native speakers of the language, the history of its development, the system of assessment criteria existing in a given language community" (Yakhina, 2008, p. 6). The researcher defines the concept of "evaluateness" as "the property of linguistic units to express a relatively stable positive or negative characteristic of a person, as well as an attitude, opinion, judgment about the positive or negative value of objects, phenomena and processes for a linguistic personality" (Yakhina, 2008, p. 6).

The phraseologism is a special way of transmitting evaluative knowledge, reflecting the value orientations of society. The phraseologism as a product of an indirectly derived nomination demonstrates the verbalized result of a three-stage process of cognition by the subject of the surrounding reality: empirical perception of the world, conceptual understanding of reality and its interpretive-evaluative understanding" (Babushkina, 2010).

The estimated value of a phraseological unit (positive or negative) is determined using cultural information related to the etymology of the phraseological unit. Evaluative meaning is interpreted as "information containing data on the value relationship of the subject of speech... to a certain property of the signified, highlighted in relation to one or another aspect of consideration of the object" (Teliya, 1986, p.54).

When determining evaluateness in the composition of phraseological units, the most important components include: the semantics of a phraseological unit (determines the meaning of a phraseological unit), component composition, extralinguistic information, dictionary marks that carry emotive-evaluative information.

3. RESULTS

In phraseology, evaluation can be expressed implicitly. To determine the axiological meaning of a phraseological unit in this case, its definition and linguocultural information are required.

So, for example, the English phraseological unit *to be full of beans* with the meaning 'to be in a good mood, full of energy' reflects the value "Happiness". The expression originated in the field of British entertainment - horse racing. Beans were considered the most expensive but effective feed for horses, giving the animals energy and every chance of winning the race. Therefore, a person filled with energy, a groovy person is called "filled with beans" (Dictionaries and encyclopedias on Academician). The phraseologism carries a positive assessment.

The German phraseological unit *Hans im Glück* - lucky beggar (*lit.* Hans in happiness) goes back to a fairy-tale character named Hans, who has become a collective concept. This is a stupid, simple-minded, but happy person. Having received a bar of gold for his work, Hans returns home happy, but on the way he exchanges gold for a horse, a horse for a cow, a cow for a pig, a pig for a goose, etc., loses everything, but continues to consider himself a happy man (Walter, Mokienko, 2009). The phraseological unit *Hans im Glück* represents the value "Happiness" and has a positive assessment.

The anti-value "Lie" is represented in the English phraseological unit *to chew the fat* with the meaning 'to sharpen the lasses, gossip'. This idiom came to us from seafarers. In the 17th-18th centuries, during long voyages, each ship was loaded with huge supplies of food, most of which was a long-life dish - salted lard. Good perishable food ran out quite quickly, and for the rest of the voyage the entire crew was forced to eat lard. If in the first days it seemed like normal food, then after a while the monotonous food seemed disgusting. But there was no way out - I had to "chew the fat." It is by analogy with disgusting food (gossip is just as unpleasant) that this expression arose (Etymological Dictionary Online). The phraseologism carries a negative assessment.

The German phraseological unit *j-m Potjomkinsche Dörfer vormachen* (*lit.* to present to someone Potemkin villages) means 'to deceive someone by creating a better impression of something than it really is'. The expression *j-m Potjomkinsche Dörfer vormachen* in German has been known since about 1850 and is associated with the name of the Russian prince G.A. Potemkin, a statesman from the time of Catherine II, who, having decided to show the supposed prosperity of the region entrusted to him, ordered the construction of fake villages with painted huts along the route of Catherine II to Crimea. On this trip, which took place in 1787, the empress was accompanied by Prince Potemkin himself, the court, numerous foreign ambassadors and their entourage. Some of the foreign guests left their memories of the trip. Thus, the

French ambassador to the court of Catherine II, Count Segur, wrote: "Cities, villages, estates, and sometimes simple huts were so decorated and disguised with triumphal arches, garlands of flowers and elegant architectural decorations that their appearance deceived them, transforming them before our eyes to magnificent cities, suddenly erected palaces, to luxuriously created gardens" (Compte de Segcr. "Memoirs ou souvenirs et anecdotes" Paris, 1827). Although Count Segur speaks of "cities, villages, estates" and "huts" that actually existed and were decorated in every possible way, nevertheless, through the efforts of foreign authors, the opinion was soon established that there were no villages, but only skillfully painted scenery (Birich, Mokienko, 1998, 156-157). The phraseological unit reflects the anti-value "Lie" and has a negative assessment.

The value / anti-value can have both a positive and negative assessment, demonstrating the property of ambivalence. Let us illustrate this statement using the example of English and German axiological phraseological units.

The English and German phraseological units *a long-suffering Job – der hartgeprüfte / geduldig wie Hiob* (lit. much-experienced / patient Job) with the meaning 'a person who suffered a lot and who had many trials in life' have a common source of origin (the Bible). The Old Testament tells about a very righteous and happy man, whose name was Job. God was very pleased with his piety. But somehow Satan argued with God: in his opinion, if Job was deprived of wealth and happiness, he would become evil and lose faith into God. To prove that Satan was wrong, God allowed him to ruin Job, send him a terrible disease - leprosy, kill his children, expel him from his hometown. Nothing broke Job's faith in the justice of God, and Job was rewarded. God gave him new children and complete happiness.

Then Job arose, tore his robe, and shaved his head; and he fell to the ground and worshiped. And he said: «Naked I came from my mother's womb, And naked shall I return there. The LORD gave, and the LORD has taken away; Blessed be the name of the LORD». In all this Job did not sin nor charge God with wrong (Job 1: 20-22).

Da stand Hiob auf und zerriß sein Kleid und schor sein Haupt und fiel auf die Erde und neigte sich tief und sprach: Ich bin nackt von meiner Mutter Leibe gekommen, nackt werde ich wieder dahinfahren. Der HERR hat's gegeben, der HERR hat's genommen; der Name des HERRN sei gelobt! (Hiob 1: 20-22).

The phraseologisms reflect the anti-value "Unhappiness" but have a positive assessment.

Thus, English and German axiological phraseological units with a positive or negative assessment reveal the content of conventional values and anti-values. Students studying a foreign language should pay attention to this fact.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The evaluative meanings contained in English and German axiological phraseological units, to a certain extent, construct fragments of the axiological picture of the world. Comparative analysis reveals the value orientations of society and specific features of the national mentality.

As researchers rightly note, the study of the phraseological fund of a language in the axiological aspect, based on its analysis from the point of view of reflecting the values of the ethnic community in it, is one of the important problems of modern linguistics and is of a universal nature (Maksimets, 2015, p.3).

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